
Deliverable D-JRP21-WP2.18

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: RIVM, ISS

**Contributing partners: RIVM, WBVR, APHA,
VRI, ISS, PIWET, NDRVI, AGES, BfR**

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 36 months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP2.18 Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of Hepatitis E to HEVnet		
Project Acronym	JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE		
Author	Ilaria Di Bartolo, Giovanni Ianiro, Luca De Sabato (ISS)		
Other contributors	All task partners: RIVM, WBVR, APHA, VRI, ISS, PIWET, NDRVI, AGES, BfR		
Due month of the report	M56		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 31-Oct-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): via publication		

BIOPIGEE

Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of Hepatitis E to HEVnet

Aim

The purpose of this activity was to upload hepatitis E virus (HEV) sequences, collected from the BioPigee project, onto the HEV-Net platform and to analyse them to identify any clusters or correlations between strain diversity and biosecurity.

Methods

To obtain comparable sequences, an email was sent to all task participants asking them to use the protocol described by Boxman et al., 2020 (1). The protocol amplifies a region in the ORF2 (capsid protein) named ORF2f which is the most used among researchers and subsequently the most frequent in the sequence databases (NCBI and HEV-NET, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of sequences available in the GenBank (NCBI, April 2016) database along the HEV genome (Courtesy of H. Vennema, RIVM). Picture adapted by EFSA report doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4886.

Guidance was produced to standardise the selection of HEV positive (pooled faeces) samples to be sequenced and was shared among task partners. The guidance gave indications of which samples (HEV positive faeces) should be collected for sequencing, with

the scope to collect representative information for each country and for each farm, while lowering the possibility of detecting clones.

HEV-Net

The HEVnet database is a password protected database including sequences combined with metadata. The database includes sequences from humans, animals and environment strains collected. Before uploading BioPigee project sequences in the HEV-Net an agreement was signed and the BioPigee partners joined the HEV-Net network. Furthermore, the HEV-Net database entries were modified to add information collected by BioPigee. Sequences were in fact uploaded in the HEV-Net database with metadata collected in the Task 2.2 by questionnaires.

Assignment of subtypes and building of phylogenetic trees

To perform phylogenetic analysis eight datasets have been built. All datasets included the 18 HEV reference sequences (2) and a genotype 4 HEV sequence as outgroup (Acc. N.: LC022745). The HEV reference strains were a set of full genome sequences. Sequenced strains belonging to the same subtype were grouped together into a cluster where there was no gaps in the distribution of distances, and the group shared a common branch (definition by Smith et al., 2020 (2)). Twelve reference sequences were assigned to subtypes and named 3a to 3m, while six were still unclassified (2).

BioPigee partners uploaded 312 HEV sequences into the HEV-Net database, obtained from HEV positive faecal samples from pigs; 266 of these sequences also included metadata (from Task 2.2) whereas 19 sequences from Austria, 3 from Italy and all sequences from the Netherlands did not include metadata and were produced in the framework of other projects. After the removal of duplicated sequences (100% nt.id. each other), 111 unique sequences were retrieved.

The non-duplicated sequences (n = 111) were compared, using the BLASTN algorithm, to the two databases in NCBI (tot. 14.749) and HEV-Net (tot. 3.120). Sequences included in the analyses, were chosen based on three criteria: 1) >250 nt., with 2) country and 3) host information available (Figure 2 diagram).

Figure 2. Flowchart indicates the selection and evaluation of HEV sequences to produce a final dataset for analysis.

From the BLASTN output, between BioPigee sequences and the two databases, the included sequences were further selected on a three-stage process. The first included sequences showing >91% nucleotide identity to BioPigee project sequences. In the second, sequences with an identity between 91% and 98% were subsampled randomly on country and host information while those with >98% nucleotide identity were all included (figure 2).

For sequences classified in subtypes as 3g and 3*, no matches were found and phylogenetic analysis was not performed. For the subtypes 3a, 3e, 3f, 3i and 3c, five datasets were built and the duplicated sequences were removed. In Table 1, the number of sequences used to build the datasets for each subtype are reported.

Table 1. Number of sequences used to build each dataset and to draw phylogenetic trees.

Subtype	NCBI ^a	HEVnet ^b	HEV-References ^c
3a	43	7	19
3e	48	45	19
3f	93	66	19
3c	58	119	19
3i	8	4	19

a: number of sequences that matched by BLASTN and retrieved from NCBI database

b: number of sequences that matched by BLASTN and retrieved from HEV-Net database

c: 18 HEV-3 sequences and one HEV-4 sequences as outgroup

Phylogenetic analysis

For each dataset a Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree was run with 1,000 bootstrap replicates in IQ-TREE Ver. 2.2.0 software (<http://www.iqtree.org>). The phylogenetic trees were modified, adding a heatmap with host and country information for each sequence using R software Ver 4.1.2 (<https://www.r-project.org>) and the ggtree package.

Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

A multivariate data analysis was performed on the results of the phylogenetic analysis on BioPigee project sequences and the answers provided by participants to the farm biosecurity questionnaires (Task 2.2). We conducted a preliminary Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) followed by the Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components Analysis (HCPC) methodology, using the statistical software R. The HCPC approach combined three standard methods used in multivariate data analyses: principal component methods, hierarchical clustering and partitioning clustering based on the k-means method. For the HCPC analysis, the farms clustered together based upon a subset of characteristics or all characteristics, with equal weights provided to them. The metadata of biosecurity characteristics consisted of 11 qualitative variables: the country of the farm, the HEV subtype, and the answers to nine questions on relevant biosecurity measures which had previously been identified as statistically associated with the presence of HEV in a multivariate model. Both MCA and HCPC analyses were performed using the FactoMineR package and the results extracted and visualized using the Factoextra package.

Results and discussion

Identification of subtypes

The HEV subtype identification was achieved by comparing sequences obtained in the framework of BioPigee with subtype reference sequences, indicated with letters a-m for the zoonotic HEV-3 genotype. To identify the subtype of an investigated sequence, the sequence alignment was performed, followed by drawing phylogenetic trees including subtype reference sequences, to establish the percentage of identity and the p-distance displayed among investigated strains and the reference sequences. A cut-off value either of percentage of identity or of p-distance was not established due to high heterogeneity of sequences (2). Subsequently, for subtype identification the comparison against all subtype references is needed.

Eight European countries, BioPigee partners', uploaded 312 sequences from HEV positive pig fecal samples, corresponding to 350bp fragment within the ORF2 (coding for the capsid protein). Each country analysed samples from pigs belonging to several farms (Table 2).

Table 2. Sequences uploaded by BioPigee project members into the HEV-Net database. Overall, 266 included metadata (information retrieved from Task 2.2)

Country	Sequences submitted	Farms analysed
Austria	44	7
Bulgaria	12	8
Czech Republic	56	15
Germany	19	8
Italy	23	7
Netherlands	22	unknown
Poland	121	21
United Kingdom	15	7
Total	312 (266 with metadata)	

Nucleotide alignment was performed among sequences. No identical sequenced strains (100% nt id) were detected among countries. Only identical sequences from strains detected

within and between farms in the same country were detected (Table 2). Presence and persistence of the same unique strain in pig farms was described in several studies, indicating that the same strain can persist up to six years (3, 4). The reasons can be several, including the persistence of HEV strains in the farm environment due to its resistance to common procedures of disinfection applied in farms, also after all-in/all-out pig management procedures, where newly introduced, susceptible pigs can be infected with the same strain (3.4).

Overall, 286 sequenced strains were clearly assigned (see Methods for the phylogenetic analyses) to 6 HEV-3 subtypes, already known and circulating in Europe, while 26 sequences, that were indicated as 3*, were not classifiable due to their nucleotide distance to all other known subtypes (Table 3, Table 4).

Table 3. Summary of HEV subtypes identified for each country.

Subtype	Austria	Bulgaria	Czech Republic	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	United Kingdom	Tot
3a	18			2					20
3c				8	3	22	9		42
3e	1	1	8	2	11		28	9	60
3f	1		30	7	9		55	6	108
3g			5						5
3i	9		5				29		43
3l			8						8
3*	15	11							26
Total	44	12	56	19	23	22	121	15	312

*Sequenced strains belonging to different subtypes but not assignable to any of the subtypes defined so far

Table 4. Nucleotide identities (percentages are reported) displayed by detected strains, within each cluster and with subtype reference strains (§).

	Austria		Bulgaria		Czech Republic		Germany		Italy		Netherlands		Poland		United Kingdom		Tot
	nt.id. within cluster	Nt. id. with reference§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	nt.id. within cluster	§	
3a	92-98	91-92					-	89									20
3c							90-95	90-96	-	95	89-97	90-96	91	95-96			42
3e	-	91	-	90	88	91	-	91	88-91	88-92			88-96	88-91	86-94	88-91	60
3f					87-99	87-88	-	93	87-95	88-89			86-99	87-92	97	89-90	108
3g					99	87-88											5
3i	91-94	90-92			-	92							92-99	90-91			43
3l					99	87											8
3*	99	87-89 [#]															13
3*			89-10	88-90 ^{##}													11
3*	90-100	86-89 ^{##}															2
Total	44		12		56		19		23		22		121		15		312

§ nucleotide identity (nt.id.) displayed by sequenced strains with subtype references indicated by Smith et al., 2020

[#]closer references: LC260517 and MF959765, identified by Smith et al., 2020 but unassigned;

^{##}closer reference: FJ705359; based on clustering the groups are not assignable to any subtypes;

Characterization of European clusters including both animal and human strains

For each subtype, a phylogenetic tree was built by analysing dataset of sequences, built as described in Methods (Table 1, Figure 1), including sequences of the same subtypes detected in the framework of BioPigee, and human and animals sequences of the same subtypes available in the NCBI and HEV-Net database.

-3a

In the framework of the BioPigee project, 20 HEV-3a sequences were retrieved from pigs from 4 European farms (Table 4). Sequences from the same farm were identical to each other (100% nt.id). The HEV-3a subtype phylogenetic tree included strains from 4 different farms located in Germany (n=1) and Austria (n=3). Pig sequences from Austria grouped in a larger cluster of Austrian strains detected mainly in pigs, but also in humans, with nt. id. ranging between 92.0% and 98%. The German 3a strain showed the highest nt. Id. with human strains detected in Hungary (94%, EF530661) and in Thailand (90%, MH450022).

-3e

A total of 60 HEV-3e sequences from 19 farm were detected from the analysed HEV positive pig faecal samples. The phylogenetic tree showed the same 3e sequences (unique strain for each farm) within 19 farms, with the exception of Polish farm PL-30, which displayed two different HEV-3e strains showing a separate clustering each other. In fact, strain PL-30-05 showed the highest nt. id. (99.8%) with two Italian strains detected in humans (MT763867) and wild boar (MT840363), while strain PL-30-07 clustered strictly (98%) with a human strain from Denmark (KU301862) and with an Italian pig strain (KP965760).

Overall, the 3e strains from BioPigee showed a mixed clustering pattern. For some strains (UK farms UK-06 and UK-09, Polish farms PL-04 and PL-13) a territorial clustering was observed, while for other cases the results highlighted the clustering of strains from farms of different countries (i.e. BG-30, Bulgaria and CZ-13, or IT-12 Italy and UK-11 United Kingdom).

A cluster of 100% nt.id. between human, pig and wild boar strains in Italy was observed. This result highlighted that the zoonotic HEV-3 strains can be retrieved in animals and humans and wild boars as well as pigs can be reservoir of HEV-3.

-3f

The HEV-3f subtype represented the most common of the BioPigee sequences (n=108; 34.6%) (Table 3-4). The 3f phylogenetic tree included 32 sequences from 22 different farms, grouped in two main large clusters. The first cluster included 4 sequences from farms located in Italy (IT-19), Poland (PL-21), Czech Republic (CZ-15) and Germany (DE-09), which showed between them 90-92% similar identity to each other, and were grouped in different subclusters.

The second cluster included 28 sequences showing in many cases an intra-country clustering pattern. Interestingly, strains from Polish farms PL-23, PL-25, PL-29, and PL-30 showed high intra-farm sequence heterogeneity (88-99%), with strains randomly grouped in different clusters. Farm PL-30 was previously described for a similar heterogeneity concerning also the HEV-3e subtype, with an overall detection in the farm of 4 different strains, 2 belonging to the 3f subtype and two to the 3e subtype.

There are two clusters between human (MZ274246_Italy_Human MZ289122_Spain_Human) and pig strains (from BioPigee), sharing up to 99% nt. Id.

-3i

Despite the low circulation in the last decade across Europe with respect to other HEV subtypes, a relative high number of HEV-3i strains were detected during the BioPigee project, with 43 sequences from 9 different farms located in Austria, Czech Republic and Poland. HEV-3i strains from each farm showed 100% intra-farm nucleotide sequence similar identity, and 9 strains were included in the phylogenetic tree. Austrian strains displayed 95.5% nt. Id (Table 4). To each other, and were grouped with human strains detected in Sweden (MH377721) and UK (strain UK-2017-203), and with pig strains from Austria (HM623777). The 3i strain from farm CZ-24 showed low correlation with previously detected HEV strains belonging to the same subtype, as well as strain PL-12-15, which presented the 96% nt id. only with a wild boar strain from Lithuania (MN545455). The remaining Polish HEV-3i strains formed a unique cluster with nt. id. ranging between 98.5 and 99.7%.

-3c

A total of 42 pig sequences from Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, and Poland were obtained from the project (Table 4). This subtype represented the only subtype reported from the Netherlands, with a high sequence heterogeneity displayed (90-96%). In fact, these were grouped separately from each other, with 11 sequences belonging to 11 different clusters.

A similar correlation degree was observed from strains detected from German farms (n=5), every strain was part of a different cluster, one per cluster. Two of the 5 clusters included sequences reported from other BioPigee countries, with high nt. id. between strains from farms DE-12 and IT-13 (96%) and between strains from farms DE-04 and PL-29 (98%). Interestingly, farm PL-29 was involved in the presence of multiple HEV subtypes from the same sampling, showing both HEV-3f (n=9), and 3c (n=3) subtypes. The HEV-3c subtype is widespread across Europe and is the most common in human cases (5, 6). Overall, sequences belonging to HEV-3c are the most strictly related to each other and to human strains, when compared to the other subtypes. This could allow a better adaptation to humans, justifying the common detection of 3c in human cases.

-3g

Two strains were retrieved from one farm in the Czech Republic, displaying 99%nt.id. By BLASTN searches, and no sequences with an identity >91% were found (Table 4). This subtype was only detected in pigs in Kyrgyzstan (7). It would be interesting to further investigate the origin of pigs in the Czech Republic farm where the strain 3g was retrieved, to understand if the animals were imported from outside EU.

-3l

Two strains were retrieved from one farm in the Czech Republic displaying 99% similar identify. By BLASTN searches, no sequences with an identity >91% were found (Table 4). This subtype, like the HEV-3g, is rarely reported. It was identified in pigs and humans only in France and Italy (2). The limited number of HEV-3l available in the databases did not allow a robust comparison and it could explain the low nucleotide identity displayed by sequences.

-3 unassigned

The unassigned strains formed three clusters, one with strains from seven farms from Bulgaria and two with strains from Austria, 4 and 2 farms, respectively. The strains from the former cluster did not cluster with any other HEV sequence. Sequences from the latter cluster clustered with two unassigned subtype references, a Japanese pig strain (LC260517) and an Italian wild boar strain (MF959765).

Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCPC)

The HCPC analysis generated five well-defined clusters (k = 7):

Cluster 1 (8/73 farms) grouped farms from Germany (87.5%) and presence of 3c subtype (62.5%). All farms had 1-5 internal persons in charge of taking care of the pigs (questionary information, Task 2.2) and purchased feed that were not tested/treated against *Salmonella* contamination.

Cluster 2 (8/73 farms) included farms from Austria (87.5%) with 1-5 internal persons in charge of taking care of the pigs and purchased feed that were not tested/treated against *Salmonella* contamination. No subtype was associated with the cluster.

Cluster 3 (32/73 farms) was partially characterized (>60%) by 6 answers: No Quarantine area present; either no Breeder area present or no cleaning and disinfection being applied in these areas; 1-5 internal persons in charge of taking care of the pigs; and external people (visitors) do not have to wash or disinfect their hands between different barn sections. Fifty percent of the farms presented 3f subtype, which is the most common subtype reported in Europe and in this project (Poland, Italy, Czech Republic and United Kingdom).

Cluster 4 (18/73 farms) was partially characterized (>50%) by 6 answers: the presence of Quarantine area; either no Breeder area present or no cleaning and disinfection being applied in these areas; 6-100 internal persons in charge of taking care of the pigs; external people (visitors) do not have to wash or disinfect their hands between different barn sections; and a farrow-to-finish farm type. Fifty percent of the farms were

from the Czech Republic. No subtype was associated with the cluster, in fact the farms had subtypes 3e, 3f, 3*, and 3i.

Cluster 5 (7/73 farms) was fully characterized (100%) by farms from Bulgaria with 3* subtype, and were those that purchased feed that was not tested/treated against *Salmonella* contamination and had either no Quarantine area present or applied no cleaning and disinfection to that areas.

Conclusions

- Phylogenetic analysis confirms the high genetic variability of HEV;
- Several subtypes circulate in EU pig farms, some subtypes are frequent (i.e. 3e, 3f, 3c), some other (i.e. 3g) are rare. The reason could be the adaptation to the host for the former, and more recent introductions in Europe for the latter;
- Except in two cases, one strain was detected on each farm;
- Similar strains, that were not identical, were detected in different countries. This could be due to the movement of infected pigs among countries;
- Only a few clusters including human and animal strains have been retrieved. These clusters belong to the subtypes for which a high number of sequences are available.
- Sequencing is needed to trace movement of strains and to identify source of infection in human cases (sequence identical in humans and animals).

Bibliography

1. Boxman ILA, Jansen CCC, Zwartkruis-Nahuis AJT, Hagele G, Sosef NP, Dirks RAM. Detection and quantification of hepatitis E virus RNA in ready to eat raw pork sausages in the Netherlands. *Int J Food Microbiol.* 2020;333:108791.
2. Smith DB, Izopet J, Nicot F, Simmonds P, Jameel S, Meng XJ, et al. Update: proposed reference sequences for subtypes of hepatitis E virus (species Orthohepevirus A). *J Gen Virol.* 2020;101(7):692-8.
3. Ianiro G, Chelli E, De Sabato L, Monini M, Ostanello F, Di Bartolo I. Long-term surveillance for hepatitis E virus in an Italian two-site farrow-to-finish swine farm. *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2021;68(5):474-82.
4. Wang H, Karlsson M, Lindberg M, Nystrom K, Norder H. Hepatitis E virus strains infecting Swedish domestic pigs are unique for each pig farm and remain in the farm for at least 2 years. *Transbound Emerg Dis.* 2019;66(3):1314-23.
5. Harvala H, Hewitt PE, Reynolds C, Pearson C, Haywood B, Tettmar KI, et al. Hepatitis E virus in blood donors in England, 2016 to 2017: from selective to universal screening. *Euro Surveill.* 2019;24(10).

6. Nicot F, Dimeglio C, Miguères M, Jeanne N, Latour J, Abravanel F, et al. Classification of the Zoonotic Hepatitis E Virus Genotype 3 Into Distinct Subgenotypes. *Front Microbiol.* 2020;11:634430.
7. Lu L, Drobeniuc J, Kobylnikov N, Usmanov RK, Robertson BH, Favorov MO, et al. Complete sequence of a Kyrgyzstan swine hepatitis E virus (HEV) isolated from a piglet thought to be experimentally infected with human HEV. *J Med Virol.* 2004;74(4):556-62.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.